

Technical Architecture

CESSDA Technical Framework Workplan phase 4, D1

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Version History

Version	Release Date	Comment
5.0.0	April 2019	Added DOI, license and telephone number.
04.00	December 2018	Following review by CESSDA CT
03.03	N/A	Added Software Licensing section. Added digital platform strategy section.
03.02	N/A	Moved to new document template.
03.01	N/A	Reviewed and updated all sections, including links.
03.00	December 2017	Added Web Usability section.
02.00	December 2016	General editing for consistency with current practice. Renamed 'Cessda Reuse Levels' to 'Software Maturity Levels'.
01.01	N/A	Baseline to create v2 from.
01.00	May 2016	Output from Phase 1 of workplan task.

Management Summary

Audience

Potential suppliers of software artefacts for the CESSDA technical research infrastructure. In the first instance, the CESSDA Service Providers, but potentially any software development organisation.

Purpose

The ambition is to promote good software development practice across the Service Provider community, in respect of the provision of software artefacts intended for use as part of the CESSDA Research Infrastructure.

It is important to ensure that the source code for every product is centrally available, so that all Service Providers can access it, thus increasing the options for maintaining and extending the various artefacts, whilst protecting CESSDA's investment in its Research Infrastructure.

The CESSDA Infrastructure follows a modern design of micro services operated on cloud infrastructure services. The publication of technical specifications and basic standards for source code quality will ensure Service Providers know what is expected of them.

The introduction of a build server linked to the source code repository ensures: that all source code is automatically tested to ensure it meets common coding standards; that there is adequate test case coverage; that basic interoperability standards have been met. It means that any need for remedial action can be highlighted well before deliverable due dates, and can act as an input to the interim and final reviews.

Without an intentional (as opposed to ad-hoc or emergent) Technical Architecture, there is a danger that the CESSDA common interoperability characteristics may be addressed in such a diverse and incompatible manner that the intended benefits do not materialise, resulting in a Research Infrastructure that is not joined up, that duplicates data and/or metadata, with components that can only be installed, configured or operated by the Service Providers that developed them.

Without an intentional Technical Architecture, there is a high likelihood that the user experience of the CESSDA RI's user community will be sub-optimal in many ways.

The combination of the development infrastructure (including the automated build and test facility) and the Technical Architecture is helping to establish

development maturity levels for both the CESSDA Research Infrastructure and the individual Service Providers. Future work plans can contain actions specifically targeted on raising the maturity levels, which will in turn reduce maintenance and development costs, whilst improving the experience of the CESSDA RI's user community.

Ideally there should be a common means of accessing all of the functionality offered by the various products (i.e. CESSDA tools will have a consistent look and feel) to ensure the User Journey is uniform and predictable, regardless of the destination. Whilst the development of such a unifying user interface component is yet to be agreed (much less planned or commissioned), following the Technical Architecture should reduce the overhead of retro-fitting such a component at a later date. In the absence of a unifying user interface, the User Experience Guide [4] is intended to help developers converge on a common look and feel.

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Glossary

Acronym	Expansion	Description
API	Application Programming Interface	<i>“In computer programming, an application programming interface (API) is a set of routines, protocols, and tools for building software and applications.”</i> Source: Wikipedia: Application programming interface
CD	Continuous Delivery	<i>“A software engineering approach in which teams produce software in short cycles, ensuring that the software can be reliably released at any time.”</i> Source: Wikipedia: Continuous Delivery
CI	Continuous Integration	<i>“The practice, in software engineering, of merging all developer working copies to a shared mainline several times a day.”</i> Source: Wikipedia: Continuous Integration
CT	Continuous Testing	<i>“The process of executing automated tests as part of the software delivery pipeline to obtain immediate feedback on the business risks associated with a software release candidate.”</i> Source: Wikipedia: Continuous Testing
CIT	Continuous Integration and Testing	A combination of CI and CT
COTS	Commercial Off The Shelf [product]	<i>“Products that are standard manufactured products rather than custom, or bespoke, products.”</i> Source: Wikipedia: Commercial off-the-shelf
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service	<i>“The hardware and software that powers it all – servers, storage, networks, operating systems.”</i> Source: Rackspace Whitepaper ‘ Understanding the Cloud Computing Stack: SaaS, PaaS, IaaS ’
PaaS	Platform as a Service	<i>“The set of tools and services designed to make coding and deploying those applications quick and efficient.”</i> Source: Rackspace Whitepaper ‘ Understanding the Cloud Computing Stack: SaaS, PaaS, IaaS ’
REST	Representational State Transfer	<i>“An architectural style consisting of a coordinated set of architectural constraints applied to components, connectors, and data elements, within a distributed hypermedia system.”</i> Source: Wikipedia: REST
RI	[CESSDA] Research Infrastructure	<i>“A seamless social science data archive service for the whole of the European Research Area (ERA), which is capable of supporting the research needs of the next generation of social scientists wherever in Europe they may be, or beyond.”</i>

		Source: CESSDA SaW project overview
SaaS	Software as a Service	<i>“Applications designed for end-users, delivered over the web.”</i> Source: Rackspace Whitepaper ‘ Understanding the Cloud Computing Stack: SaaS, PaaS, IaaS ’
SCM	Source Code Management [system]	A system for <i>“the management of changes to ... computer programs.”</i> Source: Wikipedia: Version Control
-	Software artefacts	Software products, applications, services, components.
-	Technical debt	<i>“Work that needs to be done before a particular job can be considered complete or proper. If the debt is not repaid, then it will keep on accumulating interest, making it hard to implement changes later on.”</i> Source: Wikipedia: Technical debt
-	Usability	<i>“The degree to which a product can be used by specified consumers to achieve quantified objectives with effectiveness, efficiency, and satisfaction in a quantified context of use.”</i> Source: Ergonomic Requirements for Office Work with Visual Display Terminals, ISO 9241-11, ISO, Geneva, 1998.

Scope

Software development (from requirements, through design, documentation and testing to acceptance) and deployment.

The complete in-life operations and maintenance are currently out of scope of this document. These topics are described in the wikis of the repositories contained in the [CESSDA Architectural Guidelines project](#) in Bitbucket¹, as they change frequently and need to be regularly updated.

At their core, they describe how CESSDA operates its infrastructure, designed in a microservices architecture, following the principles of the Twelve-Factor App [1]. To this end, CESSDA relies on Kubernetes to operate a Docker based solution on Google Cloud Platform.

Summary

This document provides guidance for developers of components for the CESSDA Research Infrastructure (RI). It provides guidance on meeting CESSDA's common interoperability characteristics, as they apply across the board. This is accompanied by an approach for assessing the maturity of RI components, the CESSDA Software Maturity Levels [6], so that over time CESSDA can mandate minimum levels that SPs and others have to meet as a prerequisite to supplying software artefacts for the RI.

Meeting CESSDA's common interoperability characteristics

The software architecture is intended to meet CESSDA's five common interoperability characteristics as follows. In each case, CESSDA's objective for the characteristic is stated, followed by the approach used to achieve it.

Loosely coupled but coordinated

Objective: enable Service Providers to retain independence, yet fully interact in an integrated service

Approach: the adoption of a (microservices architecture based on RESTful web service APIs provides a mechanism for reusing and combining software artefacts, regardless of their implementation details or coding language. The [API design guidelines](#) are intended to ensure a level of consistency (in both

¹ Note that though we do link to the explicit documentation throughout, not all resources are publicly accessible.

the calling and return structures and formats) that will reduce the burden of interacting with multiple services.

See also Twelve Factor App, number 7 ([Port binding - Export services via port binding](#)).

Sustainable

Objective: enable medium and long term investment and business change decisions to be made.

Approach: The provision of common standards (via this document), a common development and test environment (via the technical infrastructure) and deployment environment (via extensions to the technical infrastructure) and central source-code repositories will help reduce 'technical debt' and hence facilitate business-driven change to the CESSDA RI.

See also Twelve Factor App, number 1 ([Codebase - One codebase tracked in revision control, many deploys](#)).

Extensible

Objective: enable additional services to be built on or around it, including adapting to changing functional requirements over time.

Approach: New services can be added as required, as the integration point is the API. New and/or existing services can be combined as required via their APIs to meet changing functional requirements. Versioning the APIs and supporting two versions simultaneously allows services to evolve, without breaking the contract they provide to their consumers.

See also Twelve Factor App, number 8 ([Concurrency - Scale out via the process model](#)).

See also Twelve Factor App, number 9 ([Disposability - Maximize robustness with fast startup and graceful shutdown](#)).

Maintainable

Objective: enable components to be updated when IT specifications change.

Approach: Provided the API contract is maintained, the implementation of a service can be changed as required, to take advantage of developments in software technology. The use of RESTful APIs means that the location of

services can be changed as required, to take advantage of developments in hardware technology.

See also Twelve Factor App, number 2 ([Dependencies - Explicitly declare and isolate dependencies](#)).

Standards based

Objective: enable the coordinated and planned change to all the coupled, but coordinated, services.

Approach: The provision of common architectural standards (via this document), in particular a consistent (in both the calling and return structures and formats) and versioned API will reduce the burden of change.

See also Twelve Factor App, number 4 ([Backing services - Treat backing services as attached resources](#)).

Software Development Guidelines

The CESSDA development infrastructure offers a number of benefits for potential suppliers of software artefacts for the CESSDA Research Infrastructure, not least of which is a ready made testing environment that can be used at no cost, and will increase the likelihood of software artefacts meeting the agreed acceptance criteria. Ideally, all software development efforts should follow established industry best practices. A common reference CESSDA is developing together with other RIs from related disciplines, in particular CLARIN and DARIAH, is the EURISE Network Technical Reference [10].

Software License

CESSDA mandates the publication of source code under OSI approved Open Source software licenses [7]. After a comparative review of the most commonly adopted licenses, the Apache 2 license [8] was chosen. Unless specific reasons (licence of dependencies or pre-existing work) require a different choice, every CESSDA code repository should have a file named 'LICENSE' in the top level directory, which contains the following text:

```
// SPDX-License-Identifier: Apache-2.0
```

Software code structure

Code should be well structured, commented and with minimum complexity. Code blocks should not be repeated (i.e. the DRY principle, see e.g. [Wikipedia](#)

[Don't repeat yourself](#) page), so avoid 'cut and paste' coding techniques. A good rule of thumb is for the coder to ask themselves "has this been implemented with the least amount of code necessary?"

Although no language-specific coding conventions are mandated, the 'Coding conventions for languages' section of the [Wikipedia Coding conventions](#) page is a useful reference source for language-specific guidelines, if required.

Strings in general should be externalised. In particular, messages intended to be displayed to the User via the GUI, console or other output mechanism should not be present in source code to support localisation into multiple languages. Also source code should be free of configuration information in order to comply with Twelve Factor App principle number 3 [Config - Store config in the environment](#)). Configuration information should be made available at runtime via environment variables.

Environment-specific information

The Twelve Factor App, number 10 ([Dev/prod parity - Keep development, staging, and production as similar as possible](#)) points to the need to deploy new developments quickly, involve the developers in deployment and keep the tools as similar as possible through the development, testing and deployment environments. In order to achieve this in the current climate, some form of container can be used. As [Docker](#) is the de facto standard which has been widely used in Linux environments for some time and is now available within MS Windows, its use is mandated until further notice. [Kubernetes](#) is the de facto standard for container orchestration, its use is mandated until further notice.

Although it is tempting to specify a short list of (types and versions of) operating systems, database technologies, (No)SQL tools and implementation languages, etc. to be adopted by developers and thus used in production, it would severely limit the flexibility of potential solutions over time, as well as increasing the barriers to entry for CESSDA's suppliers.

Compliance with earlier design decisions

This document is to be taken as the primary source of information about decisions intended to guide and inform the development and delivery of software artefacts by CESSDA's suppliers. As such, the latest version should be referred to before undertaking any development work on CESSDA's behalf.

That said, detailed 'how to' guides are made available via the CESSDA SCM. See for instance the [API guidelines](#) or the [guidelines for Developers](#).

Documentation throughout the development lifecycle

The following documentation types must be made available in the relevant parts of the *docs* directory of the source code repository for the software artefact, and should be maintained and updated throughout the development process, up to the acceptance testing phase:

Operational

- Installation guide (configuration details for deployment, see also Twelve Factor App, number 3 [Config - Store config in the environment](#))

Development

- Source code commented throughout
- Requirements (functional and non-functional, including wireframes for any UI components)
- API documentation, extension/developer's guide
- Systems architecture (fit with CESSDA RI)
- Technical specification (implementation details)
- Test cases and results (de facto recorded by the Continuous Integration and Test process, and are best examined there in order to ensure they are current)
- Customisation/use guide

Templates will be [provided](#) for each document type, to provide guidance on what should be included and help ensure consistency. They will also contain the rudiments of the [Secure Development Lifecycle](#).

End-user

End user documentation may be added prior to release, and is not a prerequisite for delivery. The following types are expected:

- User guide
- Tutorials
- Release notes

Acceptance

The following types of tests will be performed, prior to formal acceptance by CESSDA:

- Documentation;
- Intellectual property issues;

- Extensibility;
- Modularity;
- Packaging;
- Portability;
- Standards compliance;
- Support;
- Verification and testing;
- Security;
- Internationalisation and Localisation.

The concrete acceptance criteria to be attained will be determined by the prevailing CESSDA software maturity level (which are determined by CESSDA MO technical staff and will change over time). See the CESSDA Software Maturity Levels [6] for more details.

Suppliers should check the requirements to increase the likelihood of acceptance. They are expected to use the CI/CD environment CESSDA provides from the start of the development process, so that they address the code quality requirements it checks from the onset. Also that way, they can notify CESSDA MO when they have a release candidate, and the test results can easily be inspected as the code is already in the CESSDA environment.

Jenkins has been chosen as the CI server for the following reasons:

- Standards - a de facto standard for CI
- Familiarity - experience of configuration and/or use amongst several CESSDA SPs;
- Features - provides tried and tested CI; links with Bitbucket and other SCM systems; hundreds of free plugins available; can build and deploy containers;
- Transferability - can export job configuration details in plain text (XML) format.

Static code analysis is performed as part of the CIT cycle.

Deployment

Once built and tested, the microservices that make up each application will be stored in CESSDA's private Container Registry as Docker Images. As and when required, they are pulled and deployed in Kubernetes clusters.

The use of Docker containers provides a number of benefits, including:

- Predictability, repeatability and immutability
- Ease of working to Twelve Factor App guidelines

- Move from 'monolithic' to 'composed' applications, via microservices(one application per container)
- Ability to maintain application environment across development, staging and production deployments
- Version management and ease of reuse.

The adoption of Kubernetes for Docker container orchestration enables:

- Automatic provisioning and management of underlying cloud resources
- Autoscaling (up and down)
- Routine health checks to detect and replace hung/crashed applications
- Portability across operating systems
- Portability across clouds and on-premises deployments.

Source code management

The Bitbucket SCM system has been mandated, and each development has its own repository (or suite of repositories) within the [CESSDA Research Infrastructure project](#). Repositories are linked to the [CIT environment](#), so that software quality assurance can take place throughout the development phase.

The choice of Bitbucket was based on a combination of standards, familiarity, features and transferability:

- Standards - a de facto standard for SCM; supports Git and Mercurial repositories
- Familiarity - experience of configuration and/or use amongst several CESSDA SPs
- Features - provides tried and tested distributed SCM; links with CI tools such as Jenkins; has built in issue tracker and wiki
- Transferability - can export code and commit history to other Git repository hosting solutions.

In this way, the source code for products and components deployed within the CESSDA Research Infrastructure will be available to CESSDA throughout their life. No product or component will be deployed without the source code first being made available in this way (with the exception of COTS products and products built from Open Source projects).

See also Twelve Factor App, number 1 ([Codebase - One codebase tracked in revision control, many deploys](#)).

Security and Privacy

Privacy Assessment

Assess privacy Impact rating using the following guidelines (taken from the 'Simplified Implementation of the Microsoft SDL'):

- *P1 High Privacy Risk. The feature, product, or service stores or transfers personally identifiable information (PII), changes settings or file type associations, or installs software.*
- *P2 Moderate Privacy Risk. The sole behaviour that affects privacy in the feature, product, or service is a one-time, user-initiated, anonymous data transfer (for example, the user clicks on a link and the software goes out to a Web site).*
- *P3 Low Privacy Risk. No behaviours exist within the feature, product, or service that affect privacy. No anonymous or personal data is transferred, no PII is stored on the machine, no settings are changed on the user's behalf, and no software is installed.*

Steps must be taken to protect PII that are appropriate for the level of privacy risk and ensure the storage location is in accordance with EU data protection directives.

Software Maturity Levels

The contents of this section have been made into a separate document [6], in order to be able to share it more widely.

Web Usability

User Accessibility

The User Experience Guide [4] describes the general user experience for CESSDA ERIC tools and search applications, based on feedback and user group discussion of the implementation of the CESSDA Data Catalogue (previously known as the 'Products and Services Catalogue'). Wireframes and visual examples are provided to illustrate functionality only. Styling follows CESSDA ERIC branding guidelines (as of July 2018), however the document does not intend to enforce a prescriptive look and feel.

Responsive design

Use responsive web design principles [5], so that applications can be used on smartphones, tablets, laptops and desktop devices. Many popular JavaScript

libraries (such as Bootstrap) provide support for building responsive applications.

Accessibility

CESSDA ERIC is committed to following agreed best standards and good practice in web design and usability. Wherever possible, our resources are compliant with the EU Directive 2016/2102 [2].

Web Accessibility Standards

Level 3(AAA) W3C guidelines for HTML5 and Cascading Style Sheets
HyperText Markup Language 5 (HTML5)
Cascading Style Sheets Version 3 (CSS v3)
Web Content Accessibility Guidelines 2.0 (WCAG 2.0): conformance level AAA where possible and at least to level AA.

Known limitations

See the 'What's not covered' section of <https://www.levelaccess.com/eu-directive-what-is-covered/> [3].

References

- [1] The Twelve-Factor App, <http://12factor.net>
- [2] EU Directive 2016/2102, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32016L2102>
- [3] EU Directive 2016/2102 'What's covered' blog, <https://www.levelaccess.com/eu-directive-what-is-covered/>
- [4] CESSDA User Experience Guide v2, bit.ly/user_experience_2_0
- [5] Google responsive web design principles, <https://developers.google.com/web/fundamentals/design-and-ux/responsive/>
- [6] CESSDA Software Maturity Levels, bit.ly/sml_doc2
- [7] Open Source Licenses by Category, Open Source Initiative, <https://opensource.org/licenses/category>
- [8] Apache License, Version 2.0, <https://opensource.org/licenses/Apache-2.0>
- [9] Thoughtworks digital platform strategy, <https://www.thoughtworks.com/digital-platform-strategy>
- [10] EURISE Network Technical Reference, <https://eurise-network.github.io/technical-reference/>

Appendix 1 - Future Work

See the Technical Working Group Roadmap 2019 - 2022.

As CESSDA's ambition is to provide a digital platform than can serve a wide range of stakeholders, and in order to do that it needs build a solid foundation. According to Thoughtworks digital platform strategy [9], there are 5 key elements to put in place:

- Delivery infrastructure;
- API & Architectural Remediation;
- Self service data;
- Experimental infrastructure and telemetry;
- Customer touch point technology.

Source: <https://www.thoughtworks.com/digital-platform-strategy>

Future versions of this document will address these elements.

Appendix 2 - Current State of the Development Infrastructure

At the date of publication of this version of the Technical Architecture document, the CESSDA development infrastructure consists of the following groupings, known as projects:

- CESSDA Architectural Guidelines (CAG): A set of Bitbucket repositories containing documentation for developers and administrators, relating to various topics, including how to gain access to the source code repositories, how to grant access to the source code repositories, technical guidelines for API development, and documentation templates.
- CESSDA Managed Content (CMC): A set of Bitbucket repositories used by editors of managed content, such as Controlled Vocabularies and Thesauri.
- CESSDA Operations (COPS): A set of Bitbucket repositories used by platform administrators, to track their technical activities.
- CESSDA Public Helpdesk (CPH): A set of Bitbucket repositories linked to publically accessible tools and services, so that Users can log bugs and make requests for enhancements.
- CESSDA Research Infrastructure (CRI): A set of Bitbucket repositories containing source code for various RI components. Each components is allocated one or more repositories, with new ones created on demand.

Repository URLs are of the form `https://bitbucket.org/cessda/<repo name>`

Many of the repositories in the CESSDA Research Infrastructure project have:

- A linked Jenkins job, which is called by a post-commit hook;
- An issue tracker (within the Bitbucket environment);
- A wiki (within the Bitbucket environment).

In addition, the cloud-based services listed below have all been set up using a functional email account. This is to ease sharing and/or transfer of administration rights between individuals, as no personal data is associated with the accounts, and all service notifications are sent to the same inbox.

Type	Description	System (see above)	Location
------	-------------	--------------------	----------

Collaborative document management	Multi-author environment with change tracking, for non-source code file types, such as documents, spreadsheets and presentations.	Google Drive	https://drive.google.com
DVCS/SCM	Distributed version control system - repositories for storing and sharing source code.	Bitbucket (Git repositories)	https://bitbucket.org
File storage	Linkable/embeddable storage option for non-source code file types, such as documents, spreadsheets and presentations.	Google Drive	https://drive.google.com
Email	Email account to use as primary contact for all other accounts. Can be used as OpenId style login credentials for other accounts.	GSuite	https://admin.google.com
Code execution environment	Spin up containers/VMs and deploy code on demand.	Google Cloud Platform	https://cloud.google.com
Chat Room	Set up open or closed topic-specific discussion spaces, e.g. developer community (closed) and user community (open).	Slack	https://cessda.slack.com
Issue Tracker	Create and manage source code-specific discussions and (technical) details.	Per repository option in Bitbucket	https://bitbucket.org
Wiki	Create and manage source code-specific discussions and (technical) details.	Per repository option in Bitbucket	https://bitbucket.org
CI Server	Continuous Integration server, runs build and test jobs against source code repositories.	Jenkins	https://cit.cessda.eu
CIT	Continuous Integration and Testing environment. Requires a CI server, an execution environment and various build and test tools.	Combination of services	See details for each component service

System Availability Monitor	Periodically check (24/7) that web site or other HTTP(S) service is available	Uptime Robot	https://uptimerobot.com/
Container registry	Similar concept to GitHub etc - version control and access/sharing for containers	Docker Hub, Google Cloud Platform	https://hub.docker.com/ https://cloud.google.com

Service Integration

There are a number of links between components of the development environment, as detailed below. These typically ensure that a change made to one is automatically reflected in the other.

From	To	Purpose	In place?
Bitbucket	Jenkins	Post commit hook - trigger a build when content of repository is updated.	Yes* [* done on per repository/job combination, so needs to be configured for each new repository.]
Jenkins	Bitbucket	Checkout code from one or more repositories (for build, test, style check or other purposes).	Yes* [* done on per job/repository combination, so needs to be configured for each new job.]
Jenkins	Bitbucket	Include issue tracker IDs in builds for traceability	N/A* [* IDs need to be entered manually by developers as part of commit comments.]

Appendix 3 - Other documents and forms

Software Maturity Levels form - an approach for assessing maturity of software components so CESSDA can mandate minimum levels that SPs and others have to meet prerequisites for supplying software artefacts to CESSDA
bit.ly/sml_2

Contributor's Agreement form - for completion, prior to accessing CESSDA's repositories
http://bit.ly/contrib_req

Software Adoption Policy - high level view of CESSDA's requirements.
bit.ly/sa_pol2

Software Adoption Procedure - flow chart.
bit.ly/sa_proc2

Repository Request form - request a new Bitbucket repository.
http://bit.ly/repo_req